

Title

An insight review on plantibodies

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Abstract

This review article delves into the burgeoning field of plantibodies, a revolutionary approach to antibody production using plant expression systems. Plantibodies, or plant-produced antibodies, have emerged as a cost-effective and scalable alternative to traditional expression platforms. This review provides a comprehensive overview of the current state of plantibody technology, highlighting its advantages, challenges, and potential applications in the pharmaceutical and medical fields. The article explores key aspects such as plantibody expression strategies, glycosylation patterns, and downstream processing methods. Additionally, it examines recent advancements in plant molecular farming techniques, shedding light on the optimization of plantibody production for therapeutic purposes. The versatility of plantibodies in addressing various diseases, including infectious diseases and cancer, is also discussed. Furthermore, this review offers insights into regulatory considerations and commercial prospects, emphasizing the increasing interest and investment in plantibody research. In summary, this comprehensive review aims to serve as a valuable resource for researchers, scientists, and stakeholders interested in the evolving landscape of plantibodies and their transformative potential in biopharmaceuticals.

Keywords

Plantibodies, plant expression systems, molecular farming, therapeutic antibodies, antibody production, transgenic plant glycosylation, plant molecular farming, biopharmaceuticals, infectious diseases, cancer therapy, immunization, immunomodulation, downstream processing, and regulatory considerations.

Introduction

Antibodies, also referred to as immunoglobulins, constitute a class of intricate glycoproteins generated by B-lymphocytes, present in the serum and tissue fluids of vertebrates. Operating as the humoral arm within the adaptive immune system, antibodies exhibit a distinctive ability to selectively identify and bind to target antigens found on pathogens or toxins. This specific binding capability enables diverse applications, including disease diagnosis, prevention, and treatment. Typically, antibodies are constructed from a fundamental unit comprising two identical 'heavy' polypeptide chains and two identical 'light' polypeptide chains, covalently linked by intermolecular disulfide bonds^[1].

In contemporary times, the practice of molecular farming involving the use of plants for antibody production has become widespread. Plants offer several advantages over alternative production systems, particularly in terms of safety. Recombinant proteins produced in plants and subsequently administered provide an enhanced margin of safety compared to those from transgenic animals. Plant cells exhibit the capacity to correctly fold and assemble not only antibody fragments and single-chain peptides but also full-length multimeric proteins due to similar pathways in protein synthesis, secretion, folding, and post-translational modifications. Notably, plants do not act as hosts for human pathogens, ensuring increased safety^[2].

The concept of employing plants as heterologous expression hosts for recombinant antibodies, termed "plantibodies," has been in existence for over a decade^[3]. The synergy of antibody and plant engineering has resulted in the expression of diverse molecular forms across various plant species^[4]. Plantibodies, generated through genetic engineering of plants with animal DNA, function similarly to normal antibodies, despite the absence of natural antibody production in plants. Plants serve as antibody factories, utilizing their endomembrane and secretory systems to produce substantial amounts of clinically viable proteins, subsequently purified from plant tissue^[5].

The utilization of plants for recombinant pharmaceutical protein production offers advantages in terms of cost, scalability, and safety. Over the past decade, diverse antibody formats have been produced and studied in different plant species, with antibodies emerging as leaders among plant-derived pharmaceutical proteins. Transgenic plants surpass cell culture-based systems for antibody production, presenting advantages such as cost savings, rapid scalability, and ease of cultivation. Heterologous proteins, including antibodies, accumulate in high levels in plant cells,

and the processes of protein synthesis, secretion, folding, and posttranslational modifications closely resemble those in animal cells^[6-10].

The application of plant-produced antibodies in human immunotherapy and other domains is on the verge of realization. A monoclonal antibody expressed in corn, intended for human immunotherapy, has already advanced to clinical trials in the United States^[11]. Plant-produced antibodies present appealing alternatives to microbially produced ones, with the possibility of direct consumption of the plant tissue containing the plantibody, eliminating the need for purification in certain therapeutic uses^[12-13]. Safety considerations, including the absence of plant hosts for human viruses or prions, further highlight the potential of plant-produced antibodies for widespread clinical, diagnostic, industrial, and therapeutic applications, ushering in a new era of possibilities^[14].

2. Historical Development

2.1. Antibodies: an important drug-development platform

It has been nearly a century since von Behring and Kitasato were awarded the first Nobel Prize for the discovery of passive immunotherapy. Approximately 25 years later, Köhler and Milstein reported the production of monoclonal antibodies through hybridoma technology, earning them a shared Nobel Prize. The last 15 years have witnessed a resurgence in antibody therapy for human diseases, following Mullis and colleagues' description of PCR. Recent advancements in antibody engineering have revolutionized the use of antibodies as research tools, transforming their roles in disease prevention, detection, and treatment^[15]. Antibodies now represent the largest category of biotechnology-derived molecules in clinical trials, with a projected market value of five billion dollars by 2005. According to the Pharmaceutical Research and Manufacturers of America (<http://www.phrma.org>), more than 20% of all biopharmaceuticals in clinical development are antibody products. A survey indicates that over 250 companies are actively working on more than 700 therapeutic antibodies, with 220 undergoing clinical trials. The abundance of antibodies in development has spurred investigations into various production methods to enhance efficiency and reduce costs. Among these, the use of plant 'bioreactors' emerges as a promising avenue. As discussed below, the development of plant-based production for secretory IgA introduces new therapeutic possibilities not previously achievable with conventional antibodies^[16].

2.2. Secretory IgA: Production of a Novel Plantibody Isotype

While the expression of antibodies in plants dates back to the mid-1980s, the first publication on this topic appeared in *Nature* in late 1989^[18], following the efforts of two German graduate students, Stieger and Düring^[17]. Since then, various types and forms of 'plantibodies' have been developed. Initially, foreign antibody genes were introduced into plant cells using nonpathogenic strains of the natural plant pathogen *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*^[19]. Regeneration in tissue culture led to the creation of stable transgenic plants. Although early work required crossing

plants expressing each chain to generate multichain proteins, recent studies demonstrate that multiple chains can be introduced in a single biolistic transformation event^[20], significantly reducing the time needed to assemble the final plantibody.

This laboratory has specifically focused on producing secretory IgA (SIgA) plantibodies^[21]. Currently, plants are the only commercially viable large-scale system for producing this unique antibody form, as minimal levels are secreted by transfected mammalian cells^[22]. SIgA is the most abundant antibody class in the body (constituting 60% of total immunoglobulin), offering local protection on mucosal surfaces against toxins and pathogens. SIgA comprises four protein chains: heavy and light immunoglobulin chains forming the antigen-binding hypervariable region, the J chain facilitating dimerization of two IgA molecules (yielding four antigen-binding sites), and the secretory component derived from mucosal epithelial cells. Dimeric IgA, including J chain from submucosal B cells, binds to the polyimmunoglobulin receptor (PIGR) on epithelial cells, transporting IgA to mucosal surfaces. This binding initiates transcytosis to the mucosal surface, where a protease releases a portion of PIGR, known as the secretory component, used to bind SIgA. The secretory component shields dimeric IgA from proteases and denaturation on the mucosal surface. Previously, obtaining therapeutic quantities of this immunoglobulin class was challenging. The recent availability of substantial amounts of secretory IgA plantibodies opens up novel therapeutic possibilities for mucosal immune system disorders, including interventions for intestinal pathogens (e.g., hepatitis viruses, *Helicobacter pylori*, enterotoxigenic *E. coli*, cholera, etc.), respiratory pathogens (e.g., rhinovirus, influenza), and genitourinary sexually transmitted diseases (e.g., HSV, ^[18]) and contraception.

2.3. Crops and Plants Used for Plantibody Production

Various crops, including tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum* and *N. benthamiana*), cereals (rice, wheat, maize), legumes (pea, soybean, alfalfa), and fruit and root crops (tomato, potato), can be employed to produce antibodies. The choice of crop variety should consider multiple factors. Leafy crops like tobacco typically yield the highest biomass per hectare, as they can be harvested multiple times a year. Tomatoes also have a high biomass yield, but production costs are higher^[24].

Antibodies expressed in potato tubers and cereal grains remain stable at room temperature for months or even years without loss of activity, whereas tobacco leaves must be dried or frozen before transport or storage to maintain recombinant protein activity. However, protein extraction from seeds is more costly than from watery tissues like tomatoes^[25].

The presence of toxic metabolites such as alkaloids in tobacco poses a disadvantage, making edible plants without such compounds preferable as expression hosts. As pharmaceutical antibodies will mainly be produced by industry, careful evaluation of production and processing costs in different crops is essential.^[26]

3.Sources of transgenic plant

Table 1: Some examples of plantibodies that have been produced

Plant	Antibody type	Specificity	Application	Reference
Tobacco	IgA	Streptococcus antigen I or II	Dental caries	Ma <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Alfalfa (<i>Medicago sativa</i>)	IgG	Antihuman IgG	Diagnostic	Khoudi <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Wheat (<i>Triticum</i> spp.), rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>) and tobacco Potato(<i>solanum Tuberosum</i>)	scFv	Carcinoembryonic protein	Cancer treatment	Stoger <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Tobacco	scFv	Ideotype vaccine	B-cell lymphoma treatment	McCormick <i>et al.</i> (1999)
Tobacco	IgG	Surface antigen	Colon cancer	Verch <i>et al.</i> (1998)
Rice	IgG	Herpes simplex virus 2	Antiviral	Briggs <i>et al.</i> (2001)

3.1 Tobacco

Tobacco stands out among leafy crops due to its remarkable biomass yield per hectare, facilitating rapid scale-up with the ability to crop several times in a year [27]. Its swift growth has demonstrated the capacity to produce a substantial quantity of antibodies. Moreover, when grown separately as a non-food/non-feed crop, the risk of cross-contamination in the food chain by pharmaceuticals is minimized [28]. Nevertheless, the presence of toxic metabolites poses a hindrance to its utilization [29].

3.2 Alfalfa and Other Legumes

Alfalfa and soybeans represent additional leafy crops utilized for the production of recombinant antibodies. Alfalfa, being a perennial crop with easy propagation and robust biomass yield, offers potential advantages by producing recombinant antibodies as a single glycoform, contrasting with the heterogeneous collection found in other plant systems [30]. Peas, categorized as a grain legume and a valuable production crop due to its high seed protein content, currently yield only low quantities [31].

3.3 Cereals, Seeds, and Tubers

Cereals, seeds, and tubers serve as superior sources of plantibodies, especially when long-term storage is a primary consideration. They can be stored at room temperature and are easily transportable. Commonly used cereals include rice, wheat, and maize, along with legumes such as peas and soybeans [32]. Antibodies expressed in potato tubers and other cereal grains exhibit stability at room temperature for months to years, while tobacco leaves require drying or freezing for long-term storage. However, the extraction of proteins from seeds is more expensive than from watery tissues, such as tomatoes. [33]

3.4 Fruits and Vegetables

Fruits and vegetables, whether consumed raw or as partially processed materials, are suitable for passive oral immune therapy. Examples include tomatoes, bananas, and potatoes. Tomatoes, with their exceptional properties for pharmaceutical protein production, including high biomass yield and controlled growth in greenhouses, were initially employed to produce a plant-derived rabies vaccine [34]. Potatoes have been widely used in the production of plant-derived vaccines and have been administered to humans in numerous clinical trials. An example is the development of an edible vaccine expressing cholera toxin B against cholera in ripening tomato fruit, achieved

4. Methods for Plantibody Production

Several methodologies have been developed to leverage plants as bioreactors for the synthesis of pharmaceutical antibodies [37].

4.1. Conventional Approach

Figure:1 Difference between conventional breeding and GM

This method involves stable transformation and transient expression to introduce new genes into a host cell. Once the desired DNA from the transformed host cell is isolated and purified, it can be introduced into the embryo of a maturing plant intended for plantibody production. After gene insertion, followed by plant propagation in open fields, large-scale plantibody production can occur [38]. However, the purification of these proteins is a protracted and intricate process. Upon antibody isolation, numerous proteins, organic molecules, glycans, and herbicides must also be isolated, leading to a complex purification process [39].

4.2. In vitro Cell and Tissue Cultures

Figure:2 In vitro cell and tissue culture

This economically significant method involves growing plant cells in differentiated stages under controlled conditions with desired genes/proteins. The harvested material can be in the form of biomass, culture liquid, or a combination of both. This method offers the advantage of producing large amounts of recombinant proteins in a shorter time, overcoming the challenges of protein extraction and purification. While not employed for edible vaccine production, this method enhances transgenic stability by eliminating the need for sexual reproduction, thereby avoiding crossing over, segregation, and recombination issues in plantibody production [40].

4.3. Breeding and Sexual Crossing

Figure:3 Breeding and sexual crossing

This method entails transforming the host plant to introduce kappa chains of either light or heavy chains and gamma chains of either light or heavy regions. Crossing a plant with kappa chains and another with gamma chains results in the production of an antibody expressing both chains [42]. This method offers a straightforward way to produce plantibodies without the requirement for double fertilization [43].

4.4. Transgenic Seeds

Figure:4 Transgenic seeds

Some researchers advocate using transgenic seeds instead of green plant tissue for plantibody production, as green plants cannot store antibodies for an extended period due to protease degradation. Transgenic seeds, having lower levels of proteases, can store antibodies for a prolonged duration without degradation [44].

4.5. Targeting and Compartmentalization

Targeting signals can be employed to retain recombinant proteins within different cell compartments, such as the endoplasmic reticulum, chloroplasts, or intracellular space. This helps preserve integrity, protect against proteolytic degradation, and increase accumulation levels of the recombinant protein. Achieving this involves tagging the antibodies with a small peptide sequence targeted to a specific cell compartment ^[45].

5. Advantages of Plantibodies

Utilizing plants for recombinant protein production offers several advantages over other expression systems like animal, bacterial, and yeast systems ^[46]. Plantibodies function similarly to mammalian antibodies but with unique advantages compared to conventional mammalian cell methods. Plants are widespread, abundant, and fast-growing, allowing for market-ready products within a short timeframe. As a result, the cost of antibodies produced by plants is significantly lower than those from animal sources ^[47]. Additionally, plants are less likely to introduce human or animal pathogens, reducing screening costs for viruses, prions, and bacterial toxins ^[48]. Moreover, they do not elicit immune responses as animal antibodies might when exposed to foreign/non-self agents and produce a relatively high antibody yield in a shorter time ^[49]. The ease of genetic manipulation and reduced economic constraints further provide an advantage over transgenic animals. Plants also present a potential vehicle for orally delivering vaccine antigens due to their thick cell walls providing protection against gastrointestinal tract degradation ^[50].

Despite these benefits, challenges remain in plantibody production. In the downstream processes, such as extraction and purification, which constitute over half of the total cost, the purification system is expensive. Currently, a protein A-based matrix is mainly used in the purification system of plant systems ^[51]. Exploring alternative, economically feasible methods, such as using oleosin or polymer fusions for plantibody purification, becomes imperative ^[52] through *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation and controlled by the tomato fruit-specific E8 promoter [35, 36].

6. Challenges and Limitations

Despite the numerous advantages of utilizing transgenic plants for therapeutic, diagnostic, or veterinary applications, there are inherent limitations to their application. Research findings indicate potential adverse reactions in individuals exposed to plant-derived allergens, fungal contaminants, and pesticides used in cultivation. Other challenges include the inability to perform post-translational modifications on produced proteins, insufficient expression levels in certain plants, environmental constraints, allergies to plant glycoproteins and antigens, mycotoxins from impurities, as well as issues related to herbicides and plant endogenous metabolites. Furthermore, gene silencing in specific cases, distinct glycosylation patterns, and

regulatory concerns, especially for therapeutic proteins seeking approval for human use, pose additional challenges. It's worth noting that plantibodies are not suitable for infants ^[53-56].

7. Application of Plantibodies

The utilization of transgenic plants for expressing molecules with therapeutic, diagnostic, or veterinary purposes has been extensively documented in the past decade. This technological approach offers significant opportunities for the pharmaceutical industry, given the increasing prominence of biological products in pharmaceutical compounds. Several plant-derived antibodies are currently undergoing clinical trials.

7.1. Therapeutic Applications

Plantibodies find applications in treating infectious diseases, inflammation, autoimmune disorders, and cancer. Notably, tobacco-produced monoclonal antibodies (mAb) present a more feasible alternative for large-scale production of the hepatitis B vaccine compared to mAbs derived from mouse ascites fluid. Plant-produced antibodies are also being explored for treating inflammatory diseases and inducing tolerance^[57].

A groundbreaking development in plantibody applications is the creation of CaroRx, the world's first clinically tested plantibody designed to prevent and protect against tooth decay. CaroRx, a Sig A secretory antibody, is an advanced anti-*Streptococcus mutans* secretory immunoglobulin produced from transgenic tobacco plants by Planet Biotechnology. This innovative approach has undergone human trials, demonstrating its efficacy. Additionally, a tobacco plantibody against a poultry virus (Newcastle disease) has received approval from the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) ^[58].

Anti-tumor antibodies targeting Burkitt's lymphoma have been expressed in rice and wheat, while antibodies engineered against *Bacillus anthracis* were extracted from transgenic tobacco strains and proved effective in mice experiments. Another promising avenue is the investigation of plantibodies for the treatment or prevention of rabies, with a tobacco-produced rabies vaccine demonstrating safety and economic feasibility compared to traditional animal-based antibody production methods ^[61-63].

Further studies involve the experimental administration of tobacco-derived plantibodies against Lewis Y antigen in tumor cells, showing positive effects in preventing tumor formation in mice afflicted with lung, breast, ovarian, and colorectal cancers. Notably, antibodies against various cancers, such as ovarian, testicular, colon, melanoma, B-cell lymphoma, and human papillomavirus, have been expressed in transgenic tobacco and are undergoing research and approval processes for human use. Plantibodies named DoxoRx and RhinoRx for post-cancer therapy and rhinoviruses, respectively, are in various stages of completion ^[64-65].

7.2. Immunization

Active immunization refers to the development of resistance in an individual due to exposure to an antigenic stimulus, also known as adaptive immunity. In contrast, passive immunity involves the transmission of preformed antibodies to the recipient without any antigenic stimulus, and the recipient's immune system remains inactive. This type of immunity is temporary, lasting only for a short duration, typically days or weeks, until the transmitted antibodies are metabolized and eliminated. The key advantage of passive immunization is its immediate action, making it suitable for situations requiring instant immunity [66-67].

A crucial aspect of pharmaceutical polypeptide production involves generating various proteins, including cytokines, hormones, enzymes, epidermal growth factors, interferons, human protein C, and pharmaceutical foodstuffs, considered for oral immunization. Transgenic plants expressing antigens in their edible tissues could serve as a cost-effective system for oral vaccine production and delivery, potentially enabling immunization through the consumption of an "edible vaccine" for passive immunization and disease prevention [68]. Genetically engineered plants and plant viruses are also employed to develop vaccines against life-threatening human diseases such as diphtheria, cholera, and Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) [69]. While some proteins effectively induce immune responses, others may not be as effective when administered orally. Oral vaccines must be protected during their passage through the harsh environment of the stomach and intestines to reach the sites of immune stimulation [70].

7.3. Immunomodulation

Immunomodulation, a molecular technique allowing interference with cellular metabolism or pathogen infectivity, involves the ectopic expression of genes encoding antibodies or antibody fragments [71]. Applications relying on modulating antigen levels in vivo depend on the expression and accumulation of these antibodies in specific subcellular compartments and tissues. Creating crop resistance and passive immunization in plants through the expression of pathogen-specific antibodies has shown promise in reducing infection and symptoms caused by viruses and mollicutes, with progress in engineering resistance against insects [72]. Immunomodulation serves as a powerful tool for studying or altering the function of antigens in vivo, stabilizing or blocking their action. Physiological and morphological changes have been observed in plants when an artificial abscisic acid (ABA) sink was created by producing an ABA-specific scFv in the endoplasmic reticulum of tobacco and potato plants [73].

Antibodies produced in plant-based expression systems are valuable for pharmaceutical use, offering cost-effective large-scale production. Plants provide a commercially viable system, especially for complex molecular forms like secretory Immunoglobulin A (sIgA) [74]. Transgenic plants are suitable for monoclonal antibody (mAb) production due to their rapid expansion capabilities without the high capital investment associated with traditional mAb bioreactor

facilities ^[75]. Additionally, plantibodies may find applications as feed additives or in phytoremediation for human healthcare ^[76].

7.4. Bioreactors

Plant-produced antibodies find applications in the production of vaccine antigens, proteins for clinical diagnosis, pharmaceutical and industrial proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, biopolymers, and food ^[77]. Plant bioreactors are cost-effective and suitable for agricultural scale-up, allowing the production of expensive biopharmaceuticals like human lysosomal enzymes in developing countries. These bioreactors have the advantages of post-translational modifications and lack contamination by animal pathogens ^[78]. In recent years, various plant systems have been developed to use plants as bioreactors for producing recombinant antibodies for diverse purposes ^[79].

7.5. Treatment of Ebola Patients

The production of anti-Ebola virus antibodies has been explored in plants recently ^[80]. A high-yielding geminivirus-based expression system in the tobacco plant *Nicotiana benthamiana* has been employed for producing a monoclonal antibody (6D8) protecting animals from Ebola virus infection. Using similar technology and *N. benthamiana*, researchers ^[81] created an Ebola immune complex (EIC) by fusing Ebola envelope glycoprotein (GP1) to the C-terminus of the heavy chain (HC) of humanized 6D8 mAb, specifically binding to a linear epitope on GP1. Co-expression of the GP1-HC fusion and the 6D8 light chain in *N. benthamiana* leaves using a geminivirus vector produced assembled immunoglobulin, purified by protein G affinity chromatography. The resulting recombinant antibody bound the complement factor C1q, indicating immune complex formation. Subcutaneous immunization of mice with purified EIC led to high-level production of anti-Ebola virus antibodies. This represents the first published account of an Ebola virus candidate vaccine produced in plants ^[82].

8. Future Prospects and Research Trends ^[83]

The plant transient expression system is currently acknowledged as the most versatile and dependable system for drug development with excellent scalability, surpassing other existing recombinant expression systems. Utilizing this system enables the production of up to 1000 kg of vaccine biomass per year, containing 5–10 µg of the target antigenic protein per 1 g of fresh weight. The demand for large-scale production of antigenic proteins or antibodies becomes critical during disease outbreaks or epidemics, such as Ebola virus, cholera, and leishmaniasis, along with the looming threat of bioterrorism.

Despite the evident advantages of the plant transient expression system, only one cholera vaccine has received FDA approval and may potentially be deployed, for instance, in Iraq. Vaccines against influenza (both pandemic and seasonal), rabies, Norwalk virus, and hepatitis B are currently in the initial stages of clinical trials (refer to Table 2).

Obstacles arising from conflicting interests among authorities, particularly regarding traditional injected and nasal-pharyngeal vaccines, contribute to the gradual integration of the plant transient expression system into public health for prophylactic purposes. Consequently, the requirements identified for this system are mechanically inherited from those associated with traditional injected vaccines, including dosage, vaccine preparation and formulation, administration, transportability, storage, stability to temperature fluctuations, vaccination schedule, and the use of adjuvants. Additionally, ongoing research is essential to optimize the glycosylation of vaccines using UDP-transferase with broad specificity.

In the future, it may be prudent to consider sequential preventive followed by therapeutic vaccinations if preventive vaccination alone proves inadequate. Exploring this avenue of research holds significant importance.

Table 2. Vaccines on Plant Base With Ongoing Clinical Trials in Humans

Product	Disease	Plant	Stage of trial
H1N1 HA VLP	Pandemic influenza A	Nicotianabenthamiana	StageI/II
H1N1 HA VLP	Seasonal infuenza A	Nicotiana benthamiana	Stage I
NVCP	Norwalk virus	Tobacco, potato	Stage I
HBsAg (HBV) VLP	Hepatitis B	Tobacco	Stage I
HBsAg (HBV) VLP	Hepatitis B	Tobacco	Stage I
Alfalfa mosaic virus with glycoprotein of rabies	Rabies virus	Spinach	Stage I
Glucocerebrosidase	Gausher disease	Carrot tissue culture	FDA approved
MucoRice B-subunit CTB	Cholera	Rice seeds	FDA approved

9. Conclusion

In conclusion, this review article has meticulously explored the dynamic realm of plantibodies, presenting a thorough analysis of their revolutionary role in antibody production through plant expression systems. The burgeoning significance of plantibodies as a cost-effective and scalable alternative to traditional platforms has been underscored, emphasizing their potential impact on the pharmaceutical and medical fields.

The comprehensive overview provided encompasses the advantages, challenges, and potential applications of plantibody technology. Notably, the discussion delves into critical aspects such as expression strategies, glycosylation patterns, and downstream processing methods, offering valuable insights for researchers and scientists navigating the complexities of this innovative approach.

Furthermore, the exploration of recent advancements in plant molecular farming techniques illuminates the ongoing efforts to optimize plantibody production for therapeutic purposes. The versatility of plantibodies in combating diverse diseases, including infectious diseases and cancer, adds a layer of significance to their transformative potential in biopharmaceuticals.

Importantly, this review extends beyond scientific considerations to address regulatory nuances and commercial prospects, reflecting the growing interest and investment in plantibody research. By serving as a comprehensive resource, this article aspires to guide researchers, scientists, and stakeholders in understanding the evolving landscape of plantibodies. In essence, it encapsulates the current state of knowledge in this field and charts a course for the future, highlighting the promise and challenges associated with harnessing plantibodies for the advancement of biopharmaceuticals

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